

Novel hybrid co-cured carbon/glass fibre composite joints for safety critical structures

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ABSTRACT

Effectively integrating composite materials with different physical and mechanical properties requires novel joining techniques to be developed. In this paper, novel co-cured joints between conductive and dielectric composite materials have been developed for multifunctional load-bearing antenna applications. Joints were fabricated using unidirectional prepregs of carbon/epoxy and glass/epoxy and loaded monotonically to failure in uni-axial tension. Ply rupture and interfacial pull-out were the predominant failure modes observed during experimental testing. Analytical and computational models were developed for predicting joint strength and quantifying the effect of joint length. The analytical models accurately predicted the joint strengths when the joint length was either short (<1mm) or long (>>6mm). Accurate prediction of the transition region between short and long joint lengths was achieved by modeling the joints with high fidelity Finite Element (FE) models. The analytical and numerical analysis methodology developed in this study will enable the efficient design of large integrated radiofrequency transparent windows into a conductive composite structure.

1 INTRODUCTION

Efficiently joining is a challenge given their anisotropy and low strain to failure. Joining composite materials with different physical and mechanical properties introduces added complexity to the design and analysis due to stiffness mismatch and large residual thermal stresses. In addition to improving structural efficiencies, dissimilar materials may also be required to satisfy additional functional (non-structural) requirements. In multifunctional load-bearing antenna structures fabricated from conductive carbon fibre composite, structurally integrated dielectric quartz/glass fibre composite windows are required for radiofrequency transparency and additional structural strength [1]–[4]. Figure 1(a) provides schematic illustration of this structural concept. The load-bearing antenna has three regions; conductive carbon fibre composite load-bearing skin, dielectric composite window and a hybrid composite(joint) region. One method of achieving efficient load transfer between the load-bearing skin and dielectric window is to interleave the positions of the ply terminations in a cocured fabrication as shown in Figure 1(b).

Achieving maximum joint strength requires optimal selection of various joint design parameters such as ply orientations, joint length and joint configuration. The strength critical design features of these joints are the ply terminations at which high through-thickness stresses promote delamination. A number of previous studies have conducted investigations of monolithic composite laminates with ply terminations [5]–[8] and also developed similar co-cured joining techniques for hybrid carbon fibre composite/titanium laminates [9]–[11]. The focus of this study is to investigate the failure mechanism and quantify the effect of joint length on the load-bearing capacity of co-cured hybrid carbon/glass fibre composite joints (Figure 2). The following section provides experimental details of manufacturing and testing of joints under uni-axial tension including the key results. Analytical approaches and computational models developed for strength prediction are described in section 3. The major findings of the study is summarized in section 4.

Figure 1 Structural concept for multifunctional load-bearing antenna [1]–[4] (a) Integrated RF window fabricated from dielectric composite material in a conductive load-bearing aircraft skin (b) Example of a flush co-cured joining configuration to allow for efficient load-transfer between the structural skin and RF window

2 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 Materials, manufacturing and testing

The carbon and glass fibre unidirectional prepreps employed in this study were T700/VTM264 and E-Glass/MTM57 respectively. The elastic properties of the two materials obtained from manufacturer's data sheet supplemented by additional tests are shown in Table 1. The nominal cured ply thickness of carbon and glass plies were 0.21 and 0.26 mm respectively.

Joints employing a finger joint configuration (Figure 2) with a stacking sequence of $[0_{16}]$ were manufactured using conventional hand lay-up process. Prior to layup, the positions of the two ply terminations of the finger joint were marked onto a plate to assist in accurate placement of the plies. Successive plies were laid up onto the plate by aligning the edges of carbon and glass plies at their respective ply termination locations. The lay-up was then vacuum bagged and cured in the autoclave following the manufacturer's specification. Joint panels with joint lengths of 3, 6, 9 and 12 mm were fabricated. To conduct a comparative assessment, joint panels were also fabricated using similar composite materials; carbon/carbon and glass/glass. The complete test matrix outlining the different joint configurations investigated in this study are shown in Table 2. A micrograph of a carbon/glass finger joint with a 6mm joint length is shown in Figure 2(b). It is evident that the positions of the ply terminations deviate from their idealized positions (Figure 2(a)). The positional variability of the ply terminations are caused by manufacturing tolerances and movement of plies during consolidation and curing.

Joints were tested to failure under uni-axial tension using a hydraulic MTS load frame, equipped with a 100 KN load-cell, at a rate of 1mm/min. A minimum of four replicates for each joint configuration were tested.

Figure 2 (a) Schematic illustration of a carbon/glass finger joint (b) Micrograph of fabricated specimen indicating the variation in positions of the ply terminations

	T700/VTM264	E-glass/MTM57
E_1 (GPa)	120.2	34.16
E_2, E_3 (GPa)	7.467	7.87
G_{12}, G_{13} (GPa)	3.904	3700
G_{23} (GPa)	2.304	3098
ν_{12}, ν_{13}	0.32	0.27
ν_{23}	0.33	0.27
α_{11}	0.02×10^{-6}	11×10^{-6}
α_{22}	22×10^{-6}	22.1×10^{-6}

Table 1 Thermo-elastic properties of carbon fibre composite(T700/VTM264) and glass fibre composite(E-glass/MTM57)

2.3 Results

2.3.1 Stress-displacement response

Typical stress-displacement curves for carbon/carbon, glass/glass and hybrid carbon/glass joints are shown in Figure 3. Linear-elastic behavior followed by catastrophic brittle failure was observed for all configurations tested. No discernible differences were observed in the stress-displacement response for different joint lengths for both similar and hybrid composites.

Figure 3 Typical stress-displacement curves for each joint configuration

2.3.2 Failure Modes

The common failure modes observed for all the joints were ply rupture, ply pull-out and resin pocket fracture (Figure 4). In hybrid composite joints, fibre fracture of glass plies and interfacial pull-out between carbon and glass plies was observed. In addition to the positional variation of the resin pockets through the thickness, slight misalignments across the width of joint resulted in complex crack morphology. The crack morphology of the failed specimens did not change considerably with joint length. Pull-out failure in glass/glass joint was more pronounced in comparison to carbon/carbon joint which shows a more brittle failure process.

carbon/carbon

glass/glass

carbon/glass

Fibre fractures in glass plies

Figure 4 High resolution optical images showing the common failure modes; interfacial pull-out and ply rupture, for carbon/carbon, glass/glass and carbon/glass

2.3.3 Strength

The ultimate tensile joint strength for all configurations are shown in Figure 5 and Table 2. Strength of hybrid carbon/glass joints were calculated using the ultimate load and cross-sectional area of glass laminate. The highest coefficient of variation in the strength results was 7.8% which indicates a relatively low sensitivity to the manufacturing tolerances. The strength of hybrid carbon/glass and glass/glass joints are quite similar and almost independent of joint length, approximately 50% of unnotched glass laminate strength. For carbon/carbon joints, an increase in strength of 18% for joint lengths greater than 3mm was observed. The joint strength asymptotes at 6mm and no significant increase for longer joint lengths. The maximum joint strength for carbon/carbon joints was approximately to 30% of un-notched carbon laminate strength.

Figure 5 Graphical illustration of experimentally measured joint strength as a function of joint length

Joint length [mm]	Joint strength [MPa](%)		
	Carbon/Carbon	Glass/Glass	Carbon/Glass
3	605(6.0)	383(3.1)	433(3.6)
6	736(7.0)	387(0.8)	419(5.4)
9	774(7.0)	432(1.7)	409(3.9)
12	808(5.8)	402(4.3)	408(3.4)

Table 2 Average joint strengths with coefficient of variation (%) in brackets

3 ANALYSIS

3.1 Analytical Modelling

The strength of the joints, assuming perfect alignment of the ply terminations, can be calculated by considering two possible failure modes; rupture of the plies along the weakest intersection and pull-out caused by interlaminar failure (Figure 6).

3.1.1 Ply rupture failure:

The weaker intersection for hybrid carbon/glass joint is T_2 which contains half the total number of the Glass plies, ignoring the contribution of resin pocket. To account for the stress concentration induced by the resin pocket, linear elastic finite element analysis was employed to determine the stress concentration factor. The details of the approach have not been shown in this paper for brevity but the methodology was similar to that employed in [12], [6]. The ply rupture strength, σ_R , can then simply be calculated by dividing the tensile strength of the unidirectional Glass ply, $X_{11,t}$, with the axial stress concentration factor, K_{t11} .

$$\sigma_R = \frac{X_{11,t}}{K_{t11}} \quad (1)$$

The maximum K_{t11} for carbon/carbon, glass/glass and carbon/glass joints were 2.79, 2.29 and 2.5 respectively and $X_{11,t}$ for carbon and glass plies are shown in Table 3.

3.1.2 Pull-out failure:

The pull-out mechanism of the joint varies fundamentally with joint length. For short joints, load transfer occurs through interlaminar shear of the resin matrix. With increasing joint length however the interlaminar shear stresses tend to zero except at the ply terminations, where stresses are singular. Therefore, the pull-out strength for a short joint is dictated by the interlaminar shear strength and for a long joint is dependent on the interlaminar fracture toughness.

Short joint:

Assuming constant interlaminar shear stresses, τ_{13} , and linear elastic behavior, a simple of strength of materials approach can be used to calculate the tensile strength, σ_{PS} , for a “short” joint of length, L , and thickness, T ,

$$\sigma_{PS} = n \left(\frac{L}{T} \right) S_{13} \quad (2)$$

where n represents the total number of interfaces being pulled-out and S_{13} is the interlaminar shear strength. In a hybrid carbon/glass joint, the difference in ply thicknesses produces interlaminar peel stresses, σ'_{33} , which is related to the interlaminar shear stress, τ'_{13} , by Eq.(3) where α is the average taper angle (Figure 7(a))

$$\sigma'_{33} = \tan(\alpha) \tau'_{13} \quad (3)$$

The quadratic mixed mode failure criteria is employed to calculate the maximum interlaminar shear stress

$$S'_{13} = \left[\left(\frac{1}{S_{13}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tan(\alpha)}{S_{33}} \right)^2 \right]^{(-\frac{1}{2})} \quad (4)$$

Following this, the tensile strength of the hybrid carbon/glass joint is determined using the equation below

$$\sigma_{PS} = n \left(\frac{L}{T} \right) S'_{13} \cos(\alpha) \quad (5)$$

Long joint:

The pull-out strength for a “long” ($L \gg T$) joint is calculated using a Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics approach which is commonly used to determine the onset of delamination in a laminate. The specific approach employed here is developed in [13] which considers the energy balance during crack growth. The model in Figure represents the delamination of carbon plies from the hybrid region. The resin pockets are assumed to be initial cracks in the joint. The critical strain energy, G_C , required to drive the growth of the existing crack should be equal difference in the energy of the joint region before and after delamination of the carbon plies.

$$nG_C = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\sigma^2}{E_i} T - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\sigma^2}{E_f} T \quad (6)$$

where the stiffness of the joint region before and after delamination is given by E_i and E_f respectively, T is total laminate thickness of glass region and σ_{PL} is the stress at delamination. Rearranging the terms in equation yields the formula in terms of the delamination onset stress

$$\sigma_{PL} = \sqrt{\frac{2nG_C E_i E_f}{|E_i - E_f| T}} \quad (7)$$

Eq.(7) used to calculate the delamination onset stress for both glass and carbon plies. The lower of the two values are shown in the predictions.

Figure 6 Analytical failure modes (a) Ply rupture and (b) Pull-out

Figure 7 (a) Pull-out model(Short joint): Flush joint(left) interlaminar shear failure and Eccentric joint(right) interlaminar shear and peel failure (b) Pull-out model(Long joint) : Delamination of glass plies (left) and carbon plies from joint region(right)

3.2 COMPUTATIONAL MODELLING

3.2.1 Finite element model description

Finite element models of the joints were created and analyzed using Abaqus/Explicit. The geometry and mesh of the carbon/glass FE model for a joint length of 6mm is shown in Figure 8. A thin slice model of the specimen of dimension 0.5mm was used. The element dimensions, 0.2x0.5x0.1 mm, were chosen based on recommendations in [14], [15] to alleviate mesh dependency of the numerical

solution. Each ply was meshed using reduced integration continuum shell elements(SC8R). Transversely isotropic material properties, listed in Table 1, were assigned to the elements. Resin pockets were considered to be voids and hence modeled as discontinuities. All the nodes were constrained in the width direction to simulate plane strain boundary conditions. The model was fixed in all degrees of freedom at the carbon end and a monotonically increasing displacement was applied at the glass end. To simulate the effects of residual thermal stresses, a thermal analysis step was included prior to application of loads and boundary conditions.

3.2.2 Damage modelling approach

The continuum damage mechanics(CDM) model employed in this study uses the Hashin failure criteria for plane stress loading conditions [16] with a stiffness degradation approach adapted from [17], was employed to simulate ply rupture. Details of the damage modelling approach can be found in [18]. Experimentally obtained ply strengths fracture energies are listed in Table 3(a). The cohesive zone model(CZM) was employed to simulate interlaminar damage. Cohesive elements [19] with a mixed mode formulation [20] were inserted between plies. The traction laws of the cohesive elements were dependent on the respective bounding plies. For cohesive elements in carbon-glass interface, the carbon interlaminar properties were used as a conservative measure. Interlaminar strengths and fracture toughness are listed in Table 3(b).

Figure 8 Geometry and mesh of finite element model

(a)	T700/VTM264		E-glass/MTM57	
	$X_{11,t}$ (MPa)	2500	1000	S_{33} (MPa)
$X_{11,c}$ (MPa)	1200	900	S_{13} (MPa)	85.7
$Y_{22,t}$ (MPa)	40	48	S_{23} (MPa)	85.7
$Y_{22,c}$ (MPa)	200	150	G_I (KJ/m ²)	0.3
S_{12} (MPa)	85.7	64.5	G_{II} (KJ/m ²)	1.6
G_{ft} (KJ/m ²)	70	40	G_{III} (KJ/m ²)	1.6
G_{fc} (KJ/m ²)	70	40		
G_{mt} (KJ/m ²)	0.3	0.4		
G_{mc} (KJ/m ²)	0.3	0.4		

Table 3 Material properties used in the computational damage model (a) Ply strengths and fracture toughness and (b) Interlaminar properties

3.3 Comparison of Model Predictions with Experiments

Comparisons of the predictions of the analytical and computational models with experimental results for each joint configuration are shown in Figure 9. Excellent strength prediction were obtained using the FE modelling approach. The FE models that only employed a cohesive zone model(CZM) resulted in an overprediction for joint lengths above 3mm. For carbon/carbon joints, this overprediction is due to the fact that matrix damage (fibre splitting) is not accounted for resulting in the plies carrying excessive transverse stresses. For carbon/glass and glass/glass, the CZM overpredicts is

For short joints ($L < 1\text{mm}$), the analytical pull-out model for short joints gives an identical prediction as the FE model. The identical comparison is because interlaminar shear failure is dominant failure and is accurately predicted by both methods. As expected the analytical pull-model for long joints ($L > 6\text{mm}$) which employs a LEFM approach gives similar predictions as the CZM only FE model as ply rupture is not included in either approach. The analytical ply rupture model accurately predicts the ply rupture stress when the stress concentration factor in the adjacent plies is included.

Figure 9 Comparison of analytical and computational model predictions with experimental results (a) carbon/carbon (b) glass/glass and (c) carbon/glass

4 CONCLUSIONS

Co-cured hybrid carbon/glass fibre composite joints were investigated in this study using experimental, analytical and numerical methods. Fractographic observations revealed that ply rupture of glass plies and interfacial pull-out between carbon and glass plies were the dominant failure modes. The strength of the hybrid composite joint was approximately 50% of the un-notched unidirectional glass fibre composite strength. Analytical models provided accurate strength predictions in two cases; short joints (<1mm) and long joints (>transfer length). Computational models employing both continuum damage and cohesive elements were found to correlate well with the experimental results and predicted the transition region between short and long joints. The computational models showed that the transfer length of the hybrid composite joints was approximately 6mm, beyond which the increase in joint strength with increasing joint length was minimal. The analysis methodology developed in this study will enable efficient design of structurally integrated radiofrequency windows for multifunctional load-bearing applications.

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